

Coffee vs. Exercise: An Eye-Tracking Study of Break Types and Team Interaction in Developer Problem-Solving

Dear Participants,

Thank you for your interest for participating in this study. Please follow the below instructions.

Instructions

What you will do today

You will complete two short phases using a small Java project:

1. **Program comprehension:** read the code and answer multiple-choice questions
2. **Debugging:** run tests, diagnose the cause, and fix the code so tests pass

There will be a short break between the two phases.

Rules

- Do not use web search or external AI tools during the session.
- Do not edit files under src/test/java (tests).
- You may edit files under src/main/java (implementation).
- You may run tests as many times as you want.

Phase 1: Program comprehension (about 30 minutes)Goal

Understand how the pricing system computes subtotal, discount, tax, and total.

What is provided

1. The project is already opened in the IDE.
2. The project is already built; you do not need to install anything.
3. You have a short specification page describing the pricing rules.

What you should do

- Read the pricing rules specification.
- Browse the code in: src/main/java/com/breakstudy/pricing/
- Answer the **Program Comprehension MCQs (Part A)**.
- Choose the best answer for each question.
- You can take notes as you work.

Important

In Phase 1, do not change code.

When you finish the MCQs, tell the researcher.

Break (15 minutes)

You will take a break based on your assigned condition.

During the break, do not work on the project.

Phase 2: Debugging (about 25–35 minutes)

Goal: Run the tests, identify the cause of the failures, and fix the implementation so all tests pass.

Important: The issue is in the implementation code under `src/main/java/com/breakstudy/pricing/`, not in the tests.

You may read tests to understand expected behavior, but you must not edit them.

Step-by-step

1. Run the tests:

- Terminal: `mvn test`
- Or IDE: run the test class `PricingEngineTest`

2. Review the failure information:

- Check which test(s) failed and compare the *expected vs actual* values shown in the terminal output.
- You can also open the **detailed test report** in `target/surefire-reports/`.

3. Answer the Debugging MCQs (Part B) based on the failures you observed.

4. Fix the bug in the implementation:

- Only edit files under `src/main/java/com/breakstudy/pricing/`.
- Do not modify anything under `src/test/java/`.

5. Re-run the tests until all tests pass (BUILD SUCCESS).

6. When finished, tell the researcher.

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. Please indicate whether or not you consent to participate. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Part1: Demographic questions

3. What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

Prefer not to say

4. How many years of experience do you have in software development? *

5. What positions did you serve in your software development career? (Please select multiple options, if you had experience) *

Check all that apply.

- Academic Researcher (PostDoc/Faculty)
- Open-source Contributor
- Project manager
- Developer
- System Analyst/Architect
- Tester
- Database Administrator
- Network Administrator
- AI Engineer
- Other: _____

6. Which type of break were you accommodated in?

Mark only one oval.

- Coffee - group
- Coffee -single
- Exercise - group
- Exercise -single
- No break

Part 2: Program comprehension MCQs (30 minutes)

7. **Q1.** Which class is responsible for computing the final tax value in the receipt? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Cart
- B) PricingEngine
- C) Promotion
- D) Receipt
- Other: _____

8. **Q2.** In checkout, what quantity is used to allocate the discount to the taxable portion of items? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) $\text{taxableItemsSubtotal} / (\text{itemsSubtotal} + \text{shipping})$
- B) $\text{taxableItemsSubtotal} / \text{itemsSubtotal}$
- C) $\text{discountAmount} / \text{taxableItemsSubtotal}$
- D) $\text{shipping} / \text{itemsSubtotal}$
- Other: _____

9. **Q3.** Where is rounding to 2 decimals applied to each item's lineTotal in the receipt? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Only at the end when computing total
- B) When ReceiptLine is created (line total computed and rounded)
- C) Only inside PercentOffPromotion.computeDiscount
- D) Nowhere, calculations use full precision throughout

10. **Q4.** If `itemsSubtotal == 0.00`, what is the value of `discountTaxable` according to the code? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Throws an exception
- B) Equals `discountAmount`
- C) 0.00
- D) Equals shipping
- Other: _____

11. **Q5.** If `shippingTaxable == false`, how does shipping affect `taxableBase`? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Always added to `taxableBase`
- B) Added only when there is a promotion
- C) Never added to `taxableBase`
- D) Subtracted from `taxableBase`
- Other: _____

12. **Q6.** Consider this cart: `taxRate = 0.05`, `shippingTaxable = false`, `promotion = 10% off`. *

Taxable item A: $\$19.99 \times 1$

Non-taxable item B: $\$10.00 \times 1$

Shipping: $\$5.00$

Assume promotion construction succeeds. According to the code, what is `discountAmount`?

Mark only one oval.

- A) $\$3.00$
- B) $\$3.50$
- C) $\$2.00$
- D) $\$0.90$
- Other: _____

13. **Q7.** Same cart as Q6. According to the code, what is discountTaxable? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) \$1.99
- B) \$2.00
- C) \$2.33
- D) \$3.00
- Other: _____

14. **Q8.** Same cart as Q6. According to the code, what is the final tax? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) \$0.85
- B) \$0.88
- C) \$0.90
- D) \$0.95
- Other: _____

15. **Q9.** When PricingEngine calls promotion.computeDiscount(baseAmount), which implementation runs? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Always Promotion.computeDiscount(...) because the variable type is Promotion
- B) Always PercentOffPromotion.computeDiscount(...) because the object is PercentOffPromotion
- C) Both run in sequence (super then child)
- D) Neither runs, because Java resolves method calls only at compile time
- Other: _____

16. **Q10.** A subclass defines `computeDiscount(BigDecimal baseAmount, boolean includeShipping)` while the superclass defines `computeDiscount(BigDecimal baseAmount)`. Which statement is true? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) This is overriding, so calls will dispatch to the subclass method
- B) This is overloading, so calls with one argument still resolve to the superclass method
- C) Java will automatically convert it to an override at runtime
- D) The compiler will reject the class due to ambiguous method resolution
- Other: _____

Part 3: NASA-TLX Questions (Pre-break)

17. MENTAL DEMAND-How mentally demanding was the task? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

18. PHYSICAL DEMAND-How physically demanding was the task? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

19. TEMPORAL DEMAND-How hurried or rushed was the pace of the task? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

20. PERFORMANCE-How successful were you in accomplishing what you were asked to do? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Good Poor

21. EFFORT-How hard did you have to work to accomplish your level of performance? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

22. FRUSTRATION-How insecure, discouraged, irritated, stressed, and annoyed were you? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

Part 4

If you are assigned to the coffee or exercise break group, please take a 15-minute break. Otherwise, you may proceed with the next part of the study.

Part 5: Question/Answering

23. B1. After running the tests, what is the main symptom? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Wrong totals (assertion mismatch)
- B) Program crashes before assertions
- C) Compilation fails
- D) Tests are skipped
- Other: _____

24. B2. Based on the stack trace, which layer triggers the failure? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Test layer
- B) Engine layer
- C) Promotion layer
- D) Money/rounding layer
- Other: _____

25. B3. What is the most likely *reason* the Promotion layer triggers it? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) A null value in the cart data
- B) A method is invoked that is not implemented for this concrete promotion
- C) Integer overflow
- D) Rounding mode inconsistency
- Other: _____

26. B4. Which investigation step is most appropriate *next*? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Inspect Money.round2 and tax math
- B) Inspect the promotion subclass for a method that should supply discount behavior
- C) Reorder the checkout calculations
- D) Remove shipping and rerun tests
- Other: _____

27. B5. Which statement about method resolution is most relevant here? *

Mark only one oval.

- A) Overloaded methods are chosen at runtime based on the object
- B) Overridden methods are chosen at runtime based on the object
- C) Overridden methods are chosen only at compile time
- D) Exceptions are resolved at compile time
- Other: _____

Part 6: NASA-TLX Questions (After break)

28. MENTAL DEMAND-How mentally demanding was the task? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

29. PHYSICAL DEMAND-How physically demanding was the task? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

30. TEMPORAL DEMAND-How hurried or rushed was the pace of the task? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

31. PERFORMANCE-How successful were you in accomplishing what you were asked to do? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Good Poor

32. EFFORT-How hard did you have to work to accomplish your level of performance? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

33. FRUSTRATION-How insecure, discouraged, irritated, stressed, and annoyed were you? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Low High

End of the user study

Thank you for participation

34. Please enter your email id for e-transfer the remuneration. *

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